

Parallel Assemblies Plot, a visualization tool to explore categorical and quantitative data: application to digital mobility outcomes

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Fig. 1: Visualization metaphor enabling the identification of a correlation between variables *disease*, *period* and *type of bout* and a correlation between the *type of bout* and *bout time*.

Abstract—This paper presents a tool enabling the visual analysis of multivariate heterogeneous data. Large amounts of measured and contextual data are being gathered for a large number of applications, increasing connectivity across different data types. While measured data are often quantitative, contextual data tend to be categorical. This results in datasets containing multivariate data with heterogeneous properties. Difference in the natures of these properties raises challenges when combining them for analysis. This paper presents the design of a tool that enables the exploration of multivariate heterogeneous data by combining the strengths of Parallel Coordinates and Parallel Sets. The design relied on the application domain of real-life mobility monitoring that is particularly affected by the challenge mentioned above. To validate the suggested approach this paper presents the result of a usability evaluation, which confirms that the presented design is as efficient as other exiting tools while providing more features for correlation analysis.

Index Terms—Heterogeneous data, Multivariate data, Visualization Technique, Scientific visualization.

With the evolution of measuring instruments, the quantity of information to be processed is constantly increasing. This increase affects the volume of information, the number of parameters, and their variability. These aspects combined, despite being well-known by the scientific community, are still a challenge for data analysis.

Mobility monitoring (for health purposes) is particularly lacking appropriate solutions to interpret large amounts of multivariate heterogeneous data. Current technologies enable the recording of mobility metrics (e.g. step length, cadence, asymmetry, etc.) as well as contextual data (e.g. health condition, path characteristics, presence of a companion, etc.). These data have the potential to improve the understanding of certain pathologies, but there are currently no solutions to handle the volume and heterogeneity of this information [18].

Parallel axes plots, e.g. parallel coordinates plot (PCP) [15] and parallel set plots (PSP) [21], provide solutions for the analysis of respectively quantitative and categorical multivariate data [17]. They give access to an overview of the data [15] and permit a fast and profi-

cient learning [36]. However, they do not provide the same support for heterogeneous (quantitative and categorical) data combined.

This study investigates the use of parallel axes plots to analyse multivariate heterogeneous data. It relies on the use case of mobility monitoring to design and evaluate the outcomes. First, this study describes the challenges that biomechanical experts faced while analyzing mobility data to improve health monitoring (see Sect. 1). Then, it describes existing visualization solutions, visual features, and design choices of importance for the analysis of multivariate heterogeneous data (see Sect. 2). Thereafter, it presents the design of a visualization metaphor that aims to solve the challenge of analyzing multivariate heterogeneous data based on parallel axes visualizations (see Sect. 3). The validity of this approach is demonstrated via a usability evaluation and use-case study from free-living mobility monitoring (see Sect. 4 and Sect. 5). Finally, the visualization method and results are discussed, and suggestions are made as to future improvements and directions (see Sect. 6).

1 MOBILITY MONITORING CHALLENGES

Mobility is a fundamental contributor to human functional ability, safety, independence, physical activity, and quality of life. How well we walk is considered the 6th vital sign of health. Conversely, poor gait is related to higher mortality, morbidity, cognitive decline, dementia, and fall risk [1]. In fact, many conditions can considerably affect how we walk (e.g. Chronic obstructive pulmonary, Parkinson’s disease, Multiple sclerosis, Hip fracture recovery, Congestive heart failure, etc.). Poor gait thus becomes a symptom that needs to be detected. For instance, most Parkinson’s disease symptoms affect mobility: tremor, bradykinesia (slowed movement), rigidity, impaired posture and balance, and loss

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Manuscript received xx xxx. 201x; accepted xx xxx. 201x. Date of Publication xx xxx. 201x; date of current version xx xxx. 201x. For information on obtaining reprints of this article, please send e-mail to: reprints@ieee.org. Digital Object Identifier: xx.xxx/TVCG.201x.xxxxxx

of automatic movements [13]. More broadly, gait detriment is among the most frequent symptoms of neurology conditions [38]. Additionally, gait predicts cognitive decline, is sensitive to several interventions, and its assessment is often used as the primary clinical outcome in gait rehabilitation trials [29]. Identifying these symptoms and monitoring their evolution by assessing the way people walk is thus a key contributor to the improvement of monitoring and treating several diseases.

Clinical observation supported by subjective and low-sensitivity tools remains the gold standard in mobility assessment [10]. The lack of realism and objectiveness of such observations contributes to varying identification of clinical needs, inadequate assessment of treatment, and inefficient neurological diagnosis [22], limiting therapeutic development and clinical management [6]. All in all, this underlines the need for objective monitoring and assessment of gait [29].

Gait characteristics	
type of bout	time category of a set of steps
bout time	time length of a walking bout
mean step time	average time length in a walking bout
mean step length	average step length in a walking bout
SD step length	standard deviation of the step length in a walking bout
step length asymmetry	average value of the difference in length between consecutive right and left steps in a walking bout
Walking behavior	
steps per bout	number of steps in a walking bout

Table 1: Example of mobility metrics mentioned in this study

The miniaturization, sophistication, proliferation, and accessibility of wearable sensors and smartphones is now enabling the acquisition of signals, not only in clinical and laboratory contexts but in free-living scenarios as well. The processing of the collected signals enables access to mobility markers that are more sensitive and less affected by observer bias [9]. These mobility markers relay inner-step information like pace, variability, rhythm, asymmetry, and postural control called gait characteristics [26], and general information like volume of walking or type of activity (walking, sitting, or lying down), called walking behavior [6] (see Table 1).

For health monitoring purposes, such walking information is associated with contextual information of two types: health/personal information (like age, gender, height, weight, medication status, and health conditions) to understand the relationship between health and walking behavior, and surrounding information (like weather, walking conditions, and time of day), to control the effect of these factors on the recorded information [33, 43].

The amount of this new multivariate heterogeneous data raises novel data analysis challenges that need to be addressed before being used to monitor health. In this section, we identify some of these challenges.

1.1 Identifying flawed values and understanding their origin

First, there is a need to identify flawed values in mobility data and understand their origins. Flawed values can have several origins: technical issues with the sensor, issues with the capture, or issues with the computation. Unreasonable or inconsistent values can highlight these issues. The first data analysis need is to look for unexpected values and try to link them with other variable values to understand their origins.

1.2 Identifying outliers and their impact on the dataset

The second need is to identify outliers and their impact on the dataset. Outliers come from the variability of the measured sample. Patients have various levels of health conditions. Extreme levels may provide extreme values. These values differ from flawed values, by respecting the limit of agreement of the data, and by being concordant to other variable values. Outliers can also extend to contextual factors, such as unexpected weather or localization. These contextual factors need to be identified to ensure that they do not belong to flawed data, and in order

to support the understanding of the sample variability. The second data analysis need consists of accessing the limit of agreement, identifying values near this limit, and correlating them with other variables within measured or contextual factors.

1.3 Verifying expected correlation among parameters

The third need is to verify expected correlation among parameters. Analysts' expertise allows them to expect certain clinical/demographic/biomechanical correlations, like the velocity and the age of people (aged populations tend to walk slower than young ones). Verifying those correlations is important to ensure that the data is not biased. Following the previous example, if age is negatively correlated with the gait speed of patients, this could indicate a confounding factor that reduces the young population's velocity and thus biases the sample. The third data analysis need consists of comparing specific variables and identifying correlations among them.

Using mobility markers to monitor health involves multivariate heterogeneous data. These data need to be identified, explored and correlated independently from their nature or quantity.

2 VISUALIZATION CHALLENGES AND EXISTING SOLUTIONS

The previous section identifies the need for a tool to allow the identification of correlations of heterogeneous and multivariate data. To address this challenge, we investigate existing biomechanical tools and visualization solutions that answer the identified challenges.

2.1 Biomechanical visualization

Biomechanical visualization tools can be divided into two categories: the ones that allow monitoring motion capture and as such verify the data (eg. [3]), and those that concern the exploration of the data and thus the identification of correlation [7, 19]. In this paper, we focus on the identification of correlation.

Many existing visualization tools dedicated to identifying correlation among biomechanical data consist of multiple views to handle the huge amount of variables: chart matrices [7] or parallel coordinates [19]. These tools provide solutions for multivariate quantitative data analysis, including identification correlation, however, none of them provide an analyzing solution for more than one categorical variable as these types of variables are relatively new to the domain.

Ghayoumi and Zhao present a tool comparing Parkinson's disease markers of different population samples [12]. They rely on the design of PSP to enable a user to compare the mean values of Parkinson's disease markers with populations of different sizes and genders. Their tool provides a solution enabling the correlation of mean values of quantitative parameters (markers) and two categorical parameters (size and gender), the gender being represented on a duplicated view.

The existing biomechanical visualizations illustrate the importance of the multivariate aspect of the data. However, the complexity brought about by the data type heterogeneity is either, not addressed, or is handled by synthesizing the available information (e.g. mean values), thereby disabling access to detail. To deepen the investigation of existing solutions this paper will examine visualization solutions answering the specific challenge of correlating categorical and quantitative multivariate data.

2.2 Visualization for multivariate data

The representation of information strongly depends on the type of data and its use. Whether data variables are nominal or quantitative is described by Munzner as variable types [28]. To take into account the type of a variable when represented — and as such give plain access to the information it contains — data visualization theories rely on the use of visual variables [4]. Visual variables (color, position, shape, etc.) enhance perceptive properties when representing data. These properties are quantitative, ordinal, selective, and/or associative. Data variables can contain combinations of all four properties. As such, the choice of the enhanced property, and thereby the used visual variables, depends on the uses of the data.

To extract the most information possible from a quantitative variable and as such enhance its quantitative property requires one to choose a

visual variable that strongly enhances it. The position is one of them. Representing quantitative variables is thus mainly done by relying on position. This explains the wide use of perpendicular axes graphs like line charts or scatterplots [5].

To extend the number of variables displayed on 2D charts, and thereby represent multivariate data, one solution is to consider multiple visual variables enhancing quantitative properties. For instance, using position a third time will result in 3D representations [8] and relying on size will lead to using scatterplots. Visual variables can be combined, but the number which can be combined is still limited such that it does not solve the challenge of representing multivariate data.

The last resort is to parallelize the representation. The parallelization can be temporal, relying on interaction, or spatial, multiplying the view. Examples of spatial parallelization are scatterplot matrices, parallel coordinates plots, or mosaic plots [11]. Using such interaction extends infinitely the amount of available variables but does not enable direct comparison as variables are not displayed in the same view.

Regarding the representation of nominal variables, they only contain ordinal, selective, or associative properties such that they can be represented with visual variables that do not enhance quantitative aspect, mainly color hue or shape [30,42]. Many 2D charts rely on these visual variables to represent categorical variables [39].

Regarding the multivariable aspect of nominal data, as for quantitative data, the display of multivariate categorical data can be achieved by using all dedicated visual variables and/or parallelizing them, resulting in methods such as pixel carpet [23] and parallel sets [21].

According to Mackinlay [27], the only visual variable that consistently enhances quantitative, ordinal, and nominal properties is the position. Regarding multivariate data representation, the spatial parallelization of variables enables their direct comparison. As such, encoding quantitative and categorical variables using parallelized positions could enable the correlation of multivariate heterogeneous data.

2.3 Parallel axes solutions

Parallel coordinates plot (PCP) display quantitative variables along parallel axes [15]. Each datum is represented by a polyline whose position along the axes varies according to the values of the corresponding variables. This artifact enables the identification of a positive correlation (when the lines tend to be parallel), a negative correlation (when all the lines tend to cross in the centre), groups (when lines tend to merge at several points on one axis), or clusters (when groups are consistent on both axes). PCP often includes a coloring feature that consists of coloring the line according to the value of a selected variable [15]. Coloring the entire view according to one variable enables one to compare it to all the variables encoding the axes (a concordant coloration with one axis display indicates a correlation). PCP can also contain a brushing feature that enables one to identify clusters (a consistent selection on another axis implies a correlation) [37]. Finally, some PCP versions can also contain a bundling feature that automatically gathers the lines according to their values to strengthen the cluster identification [14]. Overall, PCP enables correlation and clusters identification of one quantitative variable with up to four more quantitative variables at a time (two with surrounding axes, potentially strengthened by bundling, one with the colored axis, and one with the brushed axis).

Fig. 2: Hierarchical splitting of categorical variables on a parallel axis display.

Regarding categorical variables, one way to display them using PCP is by mapping their values to numerical values [34]. It mainly consists of attributing a number to a categorical value, concomitantly to their order if they possess one. However, such mapping creates an overplotting effect that complicates the access to frequency information [40] and creates a divergence between the user's mental model and the visual representation of the data [21]. Some PCP versions rely on transparency to provide access to the frequency information but if the number of values in a categorical variable is significantly inferior to the amount of data, the nuance of transparency is not enough to acknowledge the frequency variation.

Parallel sets plot (PSP) also rely on the use of a parallel axis as a representation method, but instead of individual lines for each datum, categorical data are aggregated into ribbons according to their values [21]. The size of the ribbon is relative to the number of data that it contains, such that this representation enables correlation between categories of different variables. Larger ribbons meaning that more data is shared across the same combination of categorical values. The ribbons between the two first axes correspond to all combinations of values of the first two variables (if the two first variables contain respectively two and three categories and if each combination exists among the data, there will be six ribbons, see Fig. 2). For the other axes, each ribbon that is present on the previous axis will be split for each category of the new axis (if the second axis contains six ribbons and the third contain two categories, there will be twelve ribbons between the second and third axis, see Fig. 2). This splitting creates a hierarchical effect among the display of the ribbon according to the axes order. As the ribbons on the last axes correspond to the combination of all previous categories, any correlation at this stage must be considered in view of previous axes. A large ribbon between the two last axes does not only mean a strong relationship between the two values it connects but also with all other values this ribbon originates from. Such an aspect extends the correlation property to a multivariable level. PSP also provides additional tools like brushing, axes ordering or coloration [21]. It is worth noting that unlike PCP, coloration does not add another correlation dimension but supports hierarchical understanding as the coloration is linked to the first axis (coloring ribbons according to another axis will raise the question of how to color a parent ribbon whose child ribbons have different colors).

To display quantitative data with PSP one clusters their values [20]. This provides a good understanding of overall trends among the data but naturally implies a loss of information: no access to details, including outliers. A solution designed to handle heterogeneous multivariate data based on a parallel axis metaphor is the parallel bubbles plot [41]. It consists of a representation similar to PCP, where categorical values have been mapped to quantitative values, and where the frequency of categorical values are displayed using bubbles. This solution contains all the strengths of PCP, and the use of bubble solves the frequency issue on the axis. However, this tool provides frequency information only for single categories (on the axis) but not for the relationship between several variables (like the ribbon size of PSP between two or more axes). This prevents the identification of correlation between categorical axes and does not address the distortion of the user's mental model mentioned previously [21].

Fig. 3: Combinations of categorical variables on a parallel axis display (a) with a uniform color, (b) colored according to the first axis.

Another approach relying on parallel axes is StratomeX [24]. StratomeX displays categorical data using ribbons, similar to PSP. StratomeX allows coloring by any variable, independent from the axis position. This feature relies on the fact that the ribbons are not displayed hierarchically. All the combinations of values in between two axes are displayed, independently from previous ribbons (see Fig. 3a). Following the PSP example, if the two first variables contain respectively two and three categories and if each combination exists among the data, there will be six ribbons between the two first axes. Then, if the third axis contains two categories there will be six ribbons again between the second and third axes (number of categories of the second axis x number of categories of the third axis, see Fig. 3b). The ribbons next to the colored axis will be colored according to their categories and the other will be split according to the number of colored categories.

The independence between the first axes and the colored axis provides an additional correlation dimension and the absence of hierarchical constraints makes it possible to consider a mix between categorical and quantitative axes (inspired by parallel bubble set, lines could start in the centre of each category where ribbons stop). However, the independence between the ribbons prevents correlation of more than three dimensions (no more than two with the ribbons, contrarily to PSP, and one with the color) and affects users' mental model as there is no continuity of the ribbons on the axes. In addition, users report being disturbed by the rainbow effect created by ribbon color splitting (from preliminary interviews with biomechanical experts).

Fig. 4: (a) Display of all categorical combinations on a parallel axis display, ordered according to axes order and colored according to the first axis. (b) Display of all categorical combinations on a parallel axis ordered according to the second axis, then the third then the first, and colored according to the second axis.

Pilhofer and Unwin propose another solution inspired by PSP that could be used to analyze multivariate heterogeneous data [32]. In their method, data are represented via ribbons but instead of displaying all the possible combinations between two axes, it displays all the combinations on the entire representation. Following the previous example, if the three first variables contain respectively two, three, and two categories and if each combination exists among the data, there will be twelve ribbons in between each axis. To overcome the complexity that may come with such an amount of ribbons, this tool includes a sorting feature that can sort ribbons on an axis according to another variable. If the ribbons are sorted according to the axes order they will be grouped in the same manner as the hierarchical splitting (see Fig. 4a). But it is possible to group them according to another order, consistently with the color for example (see Fig. 4b). The rainbow effect is then avoidable as all ribbons with the same color would be grouped. In addition, the tool provides a solution for merging quantitative data and categorical data by splitting ribbons into lines at the top right of the representation.

Even if this tool provides a solution to all the challenges described previously, in theory, there are still concerns regarding its usability. The possibility to sort ribbons according to a variable could be seen as making the interaction more complex. Knowing that the main interest of this feature is to control the hierarchical splitting to include quantitative axes and to facilitate the use of the color, the sorting features could be paired with the coloring so the colored axis will automatically be the start of the splitting. But automating this process will reduce users' awareness due to a lack of understanding regarding the origin of the

splitting across all axes (Colored axis being the first hierarchical level, which will be the second and why? Splitting from left to right? What if the colored axis is at the top right? etc.).

The presented solutions all provide answers to either categorical or quantitative data by using ribbons or lines on parallel axes. Some of them propose solutions to merge these visualization metaphors but this often affects the correlation possibility. Finally, one solution is configurable enough to take into consideration all the challenges but such flexibility reduces its usability. In the following section, we present a visualization metaphor that aims to use the previous features while overcoming the identified drawbacks.

3 PARALLEL ASSEMBLIES PLOT

To design a visualization method that enables the identification of multivariate correlation among both quantitative and categorical variables, this paper suggests a novel approach named parallel assemblies plot (PAP). This section presents its design and the resulting features and application.

3.1 Free-living data

The design of PAP relies on a real-life walking monitoring dataset from the Incidence of Cognitive Impairment in Cohorts with Longitudinal Evaluation (ICICLE) [25,44]. ICICLE contains data recorded on people with Parkinson's disease (PD) and controls (CL). Data were collected longitudinally across six years, on an eighteen-month interval basis. Data were collected using a sensor on the lower back, from which gait characteristics and walking behaviour were quantified. These data contain approximately thirty variables among which are the type of disease, the collected period, the type of bout, the bout time, the number of steps, the mean step time, the mean step length, the standard deviation of the mean step length, and the step length asymmetry, as mentioned previously.

3.2 Design Process

The approach presented is based on a merging of PCP-based representations (polylines) and PSP-based representations (ribbons). This merging requires several challenges to be taken into consideration during the design process. Firstly, it requires a graphical solution to translate PSP ribbons to PCP polylines. Secondly, it needs to provide a solution to the fact that brushing across a quantitative axis might imply that only a part of a ribbon will be selected. Thirdly, the hierarchical splitting of PSP constrains both interactions with axis position and color and thus needs to be addressed when merging the two methods.

Fig. 5: Transition between parallel axis displays of categorical and quantitative variables.

In PSP, the position of the ribbon has no impact as the correlation is related to the size of the ribbon, whereas in PCP the correlation is directly related to the positions of the lines. This raises the question of an appropriate translation between those two different ways of apprehending and exploring the data. The solution proposed here is to consider a ribbon as an assembly of multiple lines and to draw polylines from the ribbon at the categorical axis to the quantitative axis as previously mentioned [32]. The position of the ribbons is kept according to the categorical axis, while the lines originating from the same ribbon

are internally ordered according to the adjacent quantitative axis. This solution maintains the frequency information provided by the size of the ribbon, including all information about previous categorical variables as they affect the position of the ribbons (see Fig. 5). As the connected line is positioned according to the ribbon, this feature is expected to maintain categorical correlation information and as such allow investigation of multivariate correlation (see Sect. 4).

Fig. 6: Brushing on a quantitative (a) and categorical (b) axis over heterogeneous parallel axis displays. On the quantitative axis, the brush has been done by dragging vertically through the axis while the brush has been done by clicking on the chosen category on the categorical axis.

Brushing across a quantitative axis may imply that only a part of a ribbon will be selected. To overcome this issue, ribbons were divided according to selection. Each category is then split into two parts, one colored selected part and one grey unselected part. The unselected part is drawn below the selected to avoid interference with the exploration of the selected part (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 7: Ribbons coloration according to a quantitative variable. (a) Each combination of categories is colored according to the mean value of the quantitative data it contains and ordered hierarchically. (b) Each ribbon split hierarchically is colored according to the quantitative mean value of the data items it contains.

Coloration and axis position raise interconnected challenges such that they need to be handled in conjunction. In PSP, axis position and color are connected. This is because the hierarchical splitting always originates from the first axis. If the hierarchical splitting were somehow replaced or if it could start from another axis, so could the coloring. This feature, developed in existing work [32], will be the first possibility investigated. If the sets of ribbons are considered as small ribbons representing all combinations of categories, hierarchical splitting only consists of grouping these ribbons according to the axes' order. As each combination contains data according to a unique categorical value for each variable, this solution enables the easy coloring of data according to any categorical variable and starting the hierarchical splitting from anywhere. Regarding coloring based on a quantitative variable, ribbon combinations can be colored according to the mean value of the quantitative data they contain. However, this raises a number of challenges. The first is how to order other axes. If the colored variable

is positioned first, which should come second and third? Should it be alternatively from the picked one, full right then left, or should it just be according to the previous color selection? Trying to resolve this challenge raises another one. Which order would maximize understanding, rather than confusing the user? Initial feedback when presenting the approach to potential end-users indicated that structural variations led to confusion and that the hierarchical splitting from left to right was preferred. Secondly, coloring according to a quantitative variable highlights the ribbon combination (rainbow effect) and reduces the hierarchical effect appreciated by the users (see Fig. 7a). Another possibility was to abstract from ribbon cohesion and group ribbons between each axis independently from the surrounding ribbon as done in existing work [24]. But this was rejected as it hinders comprehension and removes the sense of connection between lines and ribbons.

The colors used in PAP are differentiable enough to be perceived by a variety of users and the scale from one color to the other varies linearly in color hue and color value to prevent any perceptual biases [31]. The color differentiation has been tested by simulating several types of color vision impairments, using color oracle [16]. The need for consistent variation between color hue and color value when using a color scale comes from the fact that color value has a stronger ordinal effect than color hue [27]. Inconsistent variations will be perceived as confusing.

Finally, the hierarchical aspect was kept on starting from the first axis, consequently, the coloring was also associated to the first axis. To homogenize the interaction, if another categorical axis was picked for color it would automatically be placed first. This implies that no categorical axis should be placed in between two quantitative axes. This would also not be appropriate as the ribbons would not appear, and a choice would need to be made as to whether the lines should be ordered according to the left or right quantitative axis. Such an approach would, moreover, transform the categorical axis into a transition axis without meaning. Regarding the coloration according to a quantitative variable, having the hierarchical splitting starting from the first axis implies that coloring the ribbon according to all the ribbons' combination did not make sense. Thus only one color per ribbon was allowed, defined by the mean value of all data it contains (see Fig. 7b).

Fig. 8: PAP example making possible the identification of a correlation between the variables *disease* and *mean step length*.

3.3 Features and application

The previous design enabled the creation of a tool that contains the following features: representing categorical (ribbons) and quantitative data (polylines); coloring according to quantitative or categorical variables; moving the disposition of the axes (while keeping the categorical and quantitative variables on different sides), brushing on both types of variables; and connecting categorical and quantitative representations.

The display of ribbons allows representing the frequency of value contained in multivariate categorical data. It also enables the correlation of two, to n , categorical variables among multivariate data thanks to the interaction with the axes position. The polyline representation enables

the representation of multivariate quantitative data, the identification of trends, and the correlation of variables two by two. The interaction with the axes position enables the modification of the chosen variables. The connection between categorical and quantitative data makes possible, in theory, the correlation between categorical variables and one quantitative variable. Finally, the brushing and coloration features add another correlation dimension that can be categorical or quantitative to any other correlation analysis. All these features used together are believed to provide a solution to the identification of correlation among heterogeneous multivariate data.

Fig. 8 illustrates the use of PAP on the ICICLE data presented in Sect. 1.1. In that figure, the data are colored according to the categorical variable *disease* (leftmost). The polylines intersecting the *mean step length* variable (rightmost) are not homogeneously colored, although the yellow lines tend to have a higher value than the blue ones. This indicates that people with Parkinson’s disease (blue PD category in the figure) tend to have lower mean step length as compared to people from the control group (yellow CL category in the figure). In addition, if the same data are colorized according to the *mean step length* variable, as in Fig. 1 (third axis from right), the ribbons going through the *CL* category at the bottom of the leftmost axis tend to be bluer than the ones going through the *PD* category at the top. This means that data which belong to the *CL* category tend to have higher *mean step length* than the ones that go through the *PD* category. In addition, the ribbons that go through *CL* tend to be colored according to the order of the *period* variable (second axis from left). This means that the mean step length of people with Parkinson’s disease tends to decrease with time. Thus, *mean step length* seems not only to be correlated with *disease* but also with *period*. This figure also makes it possible to identify a correlation between *type of bout* and *bout time*, thanks to the connection between the categorical and quantitative variables.

Based on the application to mobility data, PAP enables the correlation of categorical and quantitative data for an *unlimited* amount of categorical data and up to four quantitative data (two with neighbor axes variables, one using coloration, one using brushing). These assertions validate the use of PAP as a solution to the challenge of correlating heterogeneous data. To go further, these assertions have been evaluated via a quantitative evaluation.

4 QUANTITATIVE STUDY

By enabling PCP and PSP correlation features (use of color, dynamic axes position and brushing), PAP inherits their correlation properties. The properties of the junction between ribbons and polylines still need to be assessed. This study evaluates the correlation detection performance of the junction.

4.1 Hypothesis

The junction connects categorical and quantitative data representations. In PAP, the ribbon side of a junction contains information on the frequency of all categorical parameters displayed previously (hierarchical splitting) and the polyline side contains information about the values of a quantitative parameter. On other existing tools, whether the junction is between ribbons like PSP or polylines like PCP and parallel bubble, the amount of information displayed is lower. Polyline junction, between a categorical parameter (mapped to numerical data) and a quantitative parameter, will lack information regarding other categorical variables. Ribbons junction, between a categorical parameter and a quantitative parameter (clustered to categories), will display only a summary of the quantitative data. As PAP junction displays more information than existing tools we hypothesized that PAP facilitates the correlation detection between multiple categorical parameters and a quantitative parameter.

To challenge this hypothesis, PAP correlation properties were compared with PCP and PSP properties on heterogeneous data. Quantitative values were clusters to be displayed on PSP, and categorical values were mapped to numbers to be displayed on PCP. The evaluation assesses the effectiveness, efficiency, and user satisfaction provided by each visualization method regarding the identification of correlation between multiple categorical parameters and a quantitative parameter.

4.2 Tasks

There are three correlation configurations between multiple categorical parameters and a quantitative parameter:

- *no_corr*: No correlation between any of the parameters (categorical and quantitative)
- *full_corr*: Correlation between all the parameters (categorical and quantitative)
- *simple_corr*: Correlation between some of the categorical parameters (but not all) and the quantitative parameter

Fig. 9: Schema of the evaluation display

Fig. 9 illustrates parallel axes disposition to enable junction evaluation. This disposition has been used for the evaluation.

Since only the junction is evaluated and since some tools do not display information regarding additional categorical parameters on the junction, the position of categorical parameters affects configurations. *simple_corr* can be split in two additional configurations:

- *direct_corr*: Correlation with the categorical parameter next to the quantitative parameters but not with the other
- *indirect_corr*: No correlation with the categorical parameter next to the quantitative parameters but correlation with at least one other

These four configurations (*no_corr*, *full_corr*, *direct_corr* and *indirect_corr*) lead to three correlation tasks.

4.2.1 Task 1: Simple correlation identification

Task 1 consists of identifying a correlation between the two axes at the junctions independently from other parameters. The configurations *full_corr* and *direct_corr* are considered as a correlation and the configurations *no_corr* and *indirect_corr* are not considered as a correlation.

Fig. 10: Example of evaluated visuals for task 1, for each correlation configuration (respectively correlated or not) and for each prototype (respectively PCP, PSP, and PAP).

Table 2 gives an example of the visuals presented to the participants for the different visualization methods. PCP does not display information on previous categorical data such that there are no visible differences between *full_corr* and *direct_corr*, and between *no_corr* and *indirect_corr*. PCP and PAP visuals have been randomly displayed for this task.

Method	Correlation	No correlation
PCP	Fig. 10 (a)	Fig. 10 (b)
PSP	Fig. 10 (c)	Fig. 10 (d)
PAP	Fig. 10 (e)	Fig. 10 (f)

Table 2: Examples of visuals used for task 1

4.2.2 Task 2: Indirect correlation identification

Task 2 consists of identifying a correlation between the quantitative parameter and categorical parameters not in the junction while the two junction axes are not correlated. The configuration `indirect_corr` is considered as a correlation and the configuration `no_corr` is not considered as a correlation. As PAP does not enable the distinction between `indirect_corr` and `no_corr` it is not included in this task.

Fig. 11: Example of evaluated visuals for task 2, for each correlation configuration (respectively correlated or not) and for each prototype (respectively PSP and PAP).

Method	Correlation	No correlation
PSP	Fig. 11 (a)	Fig. 11 (b)
PAP	Fig. 11 (c)	Fig. 11 (d)

Table 3: Examples of visuals used for task 2

Table 3 gives an example of the visuals presented to the participants for the different visualization methods.

4.2.3 Task 3: Full correlation identification

Task 3 consists of identifying a correlation between the quantitative parameter and categorical parameters not in the junction while the two junction axes are correlated. The configuration `full_corr` is considered as a correlation and the configuration `direct_corr` is not considered as a correlation. As PAP and PS do not enable the distinction between `indirect_corr` and `no_corr` they are not included in this task. PSP's lack of distinguishability comes from the fact that the quantitative parameter is clustered and as such does not show order within the ribbon. Evaluating PAP alone does not challenge the hypotheses but gives us insights into its performance.

Table 4 gives an example of the visuals presented to the participants for the different visualization methods.

For all the tasks, participants were shown visuals and asked if there was or was not a correlation, as defined by the task (simple, indirect or full).

4.3 Materials and method

The evaluation was made using the platform Gorilla which enables the creation and hosting of online experiments [2]. Participants were introduced to the evaluation and asked for their consent and demographic information. They were then asked to perform each task (1, then 2, then 3) for each visualization method (combination pre-generated, randomized among participants) six times: two training (supported by a description of the task) and four evaluation. The two training tasks were examples of correlated and non-correlated data behavior. The four evaluation tasks were randomly displaying a correlation or not (combination pre-generated, randomized among participants).

Fig. 12: Example of evaluated PAP visuals for task 3 for each correlation configuration (respectively correlation or not).

Method	Correlation	No correlation
PAP	Fig. 12 (a)	Fig. 12 (b)

Table 4: Examples of visuals used for task 3

The datasets used to create the pictures were fully generated and randomized (combination pre-generated, randomized among participants and tasks). The correlations in the datasets were generated by multiplying a sample of random continuous numbers by the Cholesky decomposition of a correlation matrix of factor 0.8. It results in samples correlated by a 0.8 factor. Data behaviors requiring no correlation were added with random samples. Continuous numbers were normalized to create categorical values when using PSP.

The number of correct answers and reaction times were recorded for all the evaluation tasks. Participants were asked to rank the difficulty after each task using a slider, and asked about their preferred method at the end of each series of tasks. The error rate and reaction time assess effectiveness and efficiency, while the perceived task difficulty and the user preference refer to user satisfaction.

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Demographics

A total of 21 participants were recruited. The participants median range age was 25-30 years old and participants mainly hold a post-graduate degree or a doctorate. They came from different areas of expertise but a majority came from engineering and physical science. Regarding their expertise toward the task, they mainly describe themselves as having a basic understanding of visualization tools and consider themselves as proficient in data analysis.

4.4.2 Data analysis

Results including error rate, reaction time, perceived difficulty, and preferred visualization methods numbers were analyzed using RStudio software version 3.6 [35]. For each task, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed on the error rate, reaction time, and perceived difficulty (dependent variable) according to the visualization method (independent variable). The preferred visualization methods numbers were added for each task and for each visualization method. Before performing the ANOVA, the hypothesis of normality and homoscedasticity were tested. The ANOVA was not performed on the data measured in the third task as it concerns a unique sample. The evaluation data are available at https://github.com/AlmaCantu/mobilised_eval_result_nov_2020.

The error rate corresponds to the percentage of correct answers to each set of four questions. Respectively 63, 42, and 21 samples were recorded for tasks 1, 2, and 3: numbers of participants x number of methods. One sample was removed due to loading delays on a question during task one (resulting in 62 samples instead of 63 for task 1, \downarrow 0.2%). The reaction time corresponds to the error-free reaction time of a participant per question. As for error rate, one sample was removed due to loading delays on a question during task one. The perceived difficulty sample corresponds to a participant-evaluated difficulty for each prototype (over a hundred).

4.4.3 Task 1: Simple correlation identification

Fig. 13: Mean values of metrics recorded during task1: error rate (a) and reaction time (b).

Effectiveness The overall error rate is low for the three prototypes with a mean value of 1.2% for PCP, 1.2% for PAP and 10.7% for PSP (see Fig. 13a). According to the analysis of variance, there is a significant difference between PSP and both PCP and PAP (p -value = 0.0471).

Efficiency The overall reaction time is homogeneous with a mean value of 2.271 s for PCP, 2.389 s for PAP, and 2.553 s for PSP without any significant difference (see Fig. 13b).

User satisfaction The overall difficulty is low for the three visualization methods with a mean value of 26 for PCP, 30 for PAP, and 35 for PSP over a hundred. PSP value is higher than the others but there is no significant difference. Regarding user preference for task 1, 6 participants choose PCP as their favorite method, 10 choose PSP and 5 choose PAP.

To summarize, PCP, PAP, and PSP provide a high effectiveness performance, acceptable efficiency, and low difficulty regarding the 1-to-1 correlation, however, PSP performs a bit worse on all those metrics. Despite PCP having better results, PAP does not suffer in comparison. Despite higher error rates, reaction time, and difficulty, participants tend to prefer the PSP prototype. This last result will be discussed in Sect. 6.

4.4.4 Task 2: Indirect correlation identification

Fig. 14: Mean values of metrics recorded during task2: error rate (a) and reaction time (b).

Effectiveness The overall error rate is higher for task 2 with a mean value of 42.9% for PAP and 36.0% for PSP (see Fig. 14a). While the error is higher for PAP, there is no significant difference.

Efficiency The overall reaction time is also higher for task 2, with a mean value of 2.025 s for PAP and 2.945 s for PSP (see Fig. 14b). According to the analysis of variance, there is a significant difference in reaction time for PAP and PSP (p -value = 0.0173).

User satisfaction The mean value of PAP perceived difficult for task 2 was 84 over 100 while the mean value of PSP perceived difficult was 76. These results are both higher than the result of task 1 and despite that PAP value is higher than PSP one, their difference is not significant. Regarding user preference, 14 participants choose PSP as their favorite prototype, and only 7 choose PAP.

To summarize, despite a lower effectiveness rate and a lower user satisfaction rate (both not significant), PAP provides significantly better efficiency than PSP.

4.4.5 Task 3: Full correlation identification

Fig. 15: Mean values of metrics recorded during task3: error rate (a), reaction time (b) and subjective difficulty (c).

Effectiveness The overall error rate is lower than for task 2 but higher than for task 1, with a mean value of 31% for PAP (see Fig. 15a).

Efficiency The overall reaction time is lower than for any other tasks, with a mean value of 2.325 s for PAP (see Fig. 15b).

User satisfaction The overall perceived difficulty was lower than for task 2 but higher than for task 1, with a mean value of 68 over a hundred for PAP (see Fig. 15c).

The results of task 3 cannot be compared in the same way as the results in the other tasks, but they still give an idea of the performance of PAP in task 3. The error rate and the perceived difficulty are situated between that of task 1 and task 2, while the reaction time is better than with any of the visualization methods on any other tasks. These results only provide hints about performance as they can suffer from the learning effect. An overall, PAP tends to provide positive results for a task that is not possible to perform with the other prototypes.

4.4.6 Summary

The usability evaluation indicates that PAP allows the identification of a correlation between a categorical and a quantitative variable without significant difference from PCP and with better performance than PSP. Regarding the identification of correlation between several categorical variables and a quantitative variable despite no direct correlation, PAP is significantly more efficient than PSP and PCP does not allow such identification. Finally, regarding the identification of correlation between several categorical variables and a quantitative variable despite a direct correlation, PAP provides reasonable performance for a task that neither PCP nor PSP allows.

5 QUALITATIVE EVALUATION

The use of PAP was evaluated by a panel of biomechanist experts.

5.1 Methods

Two focus groups were conducted, and sixteen people were contacted by email. They were all expert biomechanists specializing in the analysis of gait data. The participants were asked about their roles and current use of the data. During the focus groups, experts were shown the design and different features of the tool and encouraged to comment on the relevance of the tool to perform their daily tasks. The people contacted by email were asked to use the tool with their own or provided data and asked about their uses.

5.2 Results

The study identified four benefits of using the PAP. It was highly praised by experts who explicitly mentioned that PAP enabled them to perform tasks more easily or to perform tasks that they could not do before.

5.2.1 Overview of heterogeneous data

According to the participants, PAP successfully allowed them to access all data at once. They were able to grasp frequency information on the number of measures. Some explorations confirm expected results: percentage of measure per health condition and per type of movement; while others were able to identify flaws in their exploration: missing a health metric for all measures of a particular site.

5.2.2 Identification of pipeline errors

PAP allows participants to identify unexpected values indicating pipeline errors. These flaws were discovered due to the identification of correlations between algorithm performances (extracting gait characteristics) and contextual data. Some experts identified correlations between a specific algorithm's performance and the type of movement, suggesting poor performance for small steps. Another expert identified a consequent amount of missing data on a very performant algorithm, suggesting good efficiency but poor effectiveness. Algorithms were also compared across health conditions, giving expert insight into the correlation between health conditions and algorithm performances.

5.2.3 Identify outliers

PAP was also used to identify outliers and weigh their impact when reporting on the quality of the measurement. Some experts identified outlier values for specific conditions that were neglected before as within the range of overall conditions. Some outliers were linked to specific conditions, like particularly tall people or use of walking aid, improving the understanding of the data and the apparition of outliers.

5.2.4 Identification of correlation

The panel of participants was composed of experts whose main expertise was in biomechanics, however, they were all specialized in health monitoring such that they had clinical knowledge. Some mentioned that they could retrieve correlations between gait behavior and health conditions and mentioned that the tool could support health monitoring research along with diagnoses.

To conclude, PAP allows experts to perform their analysis and more. Several cases of spontaneous data discovery have been reported. In parallel, usability has been positively praised. This confirms the value of the tool when it comes to both the exploration and correlation of multivariate heterogeneous data.

6 DISCUSSION

A first point of discussion is the self-comparison of PAP in task 3. PCP and PSP cannot display the pattern in task 3, and thus a comparison with those was considered meaningless. Likewise, no other related work contained any appropriate visualization method to compare it with. Thus, a self-comparison was performed. The self-comparison cannot be used to validate the advantages of PAP compared to other methods, as for any new features, but it gives an idea of its relative performance and ability to support solving the task.

This study focused on the representation of multivariate correlation patterns and as such did not emphasize the interaction. Interaction, such as axis reordering, is believed to affect the pattern displayed, and may hence overcome some of the issues in PCP and PSP but challenges with multivariate correlation patterns needed to be addressed first. The combined effect of multivariate correlation patterns representation and axis reordering will be investigated in future studies.

The study specifically focused on the use of parallel axes as a result of several collaborations with medical experts. The author identifies that despite the use of parallel axes requiring a bit of learning, it tends to be the favored method. The same challenge should be confronted with other visualization techniques such as scatterplot matrices or heatmaps as they provide for similar needs.

The design process and the experts' user study raised many questions that were not addressed in this study but whose relevance might be the object of a complementary study. Most concerns were toward being able to rely on additional graphs to deepen the exploration once trends or outliers were identified. Another aspect concerned the level of precision of the selection. Several experts mentioned the need to manually filter the displayed data by entering range values. The design process highlights the strong impact of the order of the categorical axis on correlation tasks. Finally, some experts suggested updating the tool with more numerical information for communication purposes (mean value, standard deviation of current selection) and adding features like histogram to support the analysis.

Finally, as a matter of fact, PAP inherits drawbacks of PCP and PSP like scalability and overplotting. The scalability issue regarding the number of parameters is dwelt by allowing users to select visible dimensions. Extended work could be performed, like implementing PCA features to identify the most relevant parameters to display, but this direction was not explored in this study. Regarding the scalability issue concerning the number of categories per parameter. It is a challenge that is not addressed by this work. It is mainly due to the fact that biomechanics datasets do not face such an issue, but it would be an interesting and beneficial challenge to tackle. Finally, the overplotting issue was mentioned as an improvement for future versions. Histograms around the axes were a solution mentioned by experts.

7 CONCLUSION

This paper argues for the need of a visualization method that can handle both categorical and quantitative variables with multivariable aspects. The focus of this study was to provide a tool allowing correlation identification. The visualization domain already contains many separate solutions for each challenge. To answer the merged challenge this study relied on existing work and their limitations to design a new visualization metaphor named parallel assemblies plots. The usability of the visualization metaphor was validated through a usability evaluation with twenty-one participants. The results indicated that parallel assemblies plots provide consistent performances compared to existing visualization methods, in addition to providing new features such as a multivariable correlation between categorical and quantitative data. This work raised questions concerning the functioning of existing correlation tools, aiming to bring solutions to the ever-growing number of datasets containing categorical data and to open opportunities regarding the exploration of heterogeneous data.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to thank all the users that took part in this study. Those who volunteered to participate in the brainstorming and iterative design process, and those who participated in the evaluations. We acknowledge grants from Parkinson's UK that funded this research (J-0802, G-1301, G-1507). We also acknowledge infrastructure support provided by Newcastle Biomedical Research Centre hosted by Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals National Health Service (NHS) Foundation Trust and Newcastle University. The views expressed are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the NHS, the NIHR, or the Department of Health. We would like to acknowledge all past and present members of the ICICLE teams for their assistance with data collection, as well as participants for their contributions. Finally, the authors are supported by the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 820820. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program and EFPIA.

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